

BORROWINGS IN THE LEXICAL SYSTEM OF A LANGUAGE

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Abstract. this article deals with borrowings in the lexical system of a language. In addition, author gives several possible theories concerning borrowings.

Keywords: borrowings, paradigm, prototype, morpheme, syntactic construction.

Borrowings constitute a special layer of vocabulary, both in terms of nomination processes and in terms of motivation. Being one of the possible responses to the needs of the nomination arising as a result of language contacts and expansion under the influence of other linguistic communities of the experience of a given language community, they represent a certain economy of language efforts in speech generation, since to fill the nominative gaps that have arisen in a given language, ready-made units of a foreign language. At the same time, the loss of the previous associative links that existed in the language from which they are borrowed entails the loss of the source of motivation, possibly inherent in borrowed words in the language, which accordingly causes significant difficulties in recognizing their meaning in the process of speech perception.

Reformatsky A.A. writes about the possibility of borrowing within one language, when words from professional speech, dialects and jargons pass into the general literary language, and vice versa. It is important to note that during the transition to the general literary language, words expand their meaning, for example, the word goal, which came into use from the speech of shooters, i.e. narrower range of speech. In the reverse process, the meaning of the word is narrowed, for example, fr. officer initially denoted any serviceman, later the meaning of the word narrowed down to designate a military rank [1].

According to another theory, borrowing is a word that came from another language with the transformation of the phonetic form of the word, spelling, paradigm or the meaning of the word in accordance with the norms of the language [2]. Thus, the word adapts and only then enters the language.

There is also another point of view, which Maslovskiy E.K. adheres to. "Borrowing is not a process, but, in fact, only the initial use of foreign language material in a new language environment for it," he writes. According to this point of view, a word

cannot be borrowed, since lexical material is borrowed, which "provides a prototype for borrowing" [3].

One more approach can be singled out, according to which borrowing is both a process and an element. This point of view is reflected in the definition of borrowing, given in the Big Encyclopedic Dictionary of Linguistics, ed. Teliya V.N.: "borrowing is an element of a foreign language (word, morpheme, syntactic construction, etc.), transferred from one to another as a result of language contacts, as well as the process of transition of elements of one language into another" [4].

Borrowing as a process of using elements of one language in another is thus due to the linguistically dialectically contradictory nature of a linguistic sign: its arbitrariness as a force allowing borrowing and involuntary as a factor preventing borrowing. This, apparently, explains the fact that the process of borrowing in modern English, as, indeed, in Russian, is, according to available data, not very productive and in quantitative terms is significantly inferior to such nomination processes as described above, such as word formation and semantic derivation. This does not mean, however, that the share of borrowings in modern English is not representative. Borrowed from approximately 50 languages of the world, lexical units make up almost 70% of the vocabulary of the English language and include layers of vocabulary borrowed in various historical eras and under the influence of various historical, geographical, social, economic, cultural, etc. — conditions for the development and existence of the English language. Being the result of a long historical interaction of languages, borrowing as a process and borrowing as a result of this process are of considerable interest for the history of the language, within which they receive detailed coverage of the causes and source languages of borrowings, ways, forms and types of borrowings, as well as those transformations which the borrowed word undergoes in the language that borrowed it. For synchronous lexicological studies, borrowings are interesting, first of all, because This influence is most obvious when not only individual units are involved in the process of borrowing, but entire groups of words between which certain relations existed in the source language. An obvious case, when the presence of links between words in the source language is relevant for the borrowing language, are derivational links. A significant number of English borrowings (for example, *rural* - *L Rurialis* from *rus*, *ruris*- *qishloq*, *haydaladigan yer,dala*; *cardiac-yurakka oid* - *Gk. Kardiakos* from *Kardia* "yurak", and many others) appear in the language - source are genetically derived and are characterized by structural-semantic dependence and deducibility. Under the condition that both members of such word-building pairs are

borrowed, the derivational relations between them are preserved in the language that borrows them. *For example, gloss- izoh, belgilash izohlash – glossary-izohli lug'at; dynasty –sulola, shajara, dynastic- sulolaviy, dynastic-sulolaga oid, etc.* words. A significant number of morphologically segmented units arise, whose complexity is well felt by native English speakers, and as a result, new word-building models are formed. Thus, both the very composition of English morphemes and its derivational possibilities are significantly expanded. Interrelated to one or another type of relationship of borrowed words in the English language, not only the replenishment of the subsystem of simple and derivative words takes place. A significant number of morphologically segmented units arise, whose complexity is well felt by native English speakers, and as a result, new word-building models are formed. Thus, both the very composition of English morphemes and its derivational possibilities are significantly expanded. Interrelated to one or another type of relationship of borrowed words in the English language, not only the replenishment of the subsystem of simple and derivative words takes place. A significant number of morphologically segmented units arise, whose complexity is well felt by native English speakers, and as a result, new word-building models are formed. Thus, both the very composition of English morphemes and its derivational possibilities are significantly expanded.

The life of borrowed words in the language that borrowed them is interesting. Many of the borrowings, under the influence of the system they entered, undergo significant phonetic, grammatical and even semantic changes, thus adapting to the phonetic, grammatical and semantic laws of the given system.

The process of assimilation can be so deep that the foreign origin of such words is not felt by native English speakers and is found only with the help of etymological analysis. This is especially true, for example, for Scandinavian and early Latin borrowings like *get receive, skill-mahorat, sky-osmon, skirt-yubka, skin-teri, they-ular, street-ko'cha, etc.* Unlike fully assimilated and assimilated borrowings, partially assimilated foreign language units retain traces of their foreign origin in the form of phonetic, for example, (garage) *chaise-longue chic*), grammatical (*for example, singular datum, nucleus, antenna - pl. . datd, nuclei, antennae*) and semantic features (*for example, taiga- tundra, ruble-pul birligi*) etc. borrowings from the Russian language, denoting realities and concepts alien to the British). In order to adequately describe them in the explanatory dictionaries of the English language, lexicographers widely use encyclopedic information that informs about the places of distribution, forms of existence, methods of application, etc. designated

objects and phenomena. So, when interpreting the words *taiga*, *tundra*, along with an indication of the generic characteristics and differential features that make it possible to see the specifics and difference of these realities in comparison with the realities closest and known to native speakers of the English language, indications are given of the climatic zone, geographical area: *taiga – swampy coniferous forest of Siberia- beginning where the tundra ends; tundra- tree less plain characteristic of arctic and subarctic regions*. The description of the names of monetary units of *the ruble* type borrowed into English also implies an indication of both the fact that this is a monetary unit.

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